

India's Energy Strategy for Sustainable Development: Move towards Clean Energy

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Abstract

Developing country like India in its progress towards achieving economic growth has to depend on various energy sources to achieve its growth objective. Higher economic growth is pre-conditioned by larger dependency on energy. But the reliance on non-renewable sources of energy can contribute to environmental pollution through emission of green-house gases. The present study is an attempt to identify the strategies to achieve sustainable development through sustainable energy usage. The study has identified that by reducing the dependency on coal and other non-renewable energy sources and concentrating more on renewable sources of energy can help in achieving sustainable development without depleting the environment and its ecosystem.

Key Words: Solar Energy, Sustainable Development, Renewable sources, Environment

Introduction

Energy has been widely considered as one of the most important inputs for economic growth and human development. Economic development and energy consumption are mutually related. The growth of an economy with its global competitiveness, depend on the availability of cost-effective and environmentally friendly energy sources to achieve its development objective. Similarly, as an economy move towards higher level of economic development, the country will have to identify ways by which it can meet the growing energy demand of its citizens. India's has been witnessing increased energy consumption recently due to its increasing population and focus on economic development. Primary commercial energy demand grew at the rate of six per cent between 1981 and 2001 ((Planning Commission 2002). India accounts for about 3.5% of the world commercial energy demand in the year 2003 and ranks fifth in the world in terms of primary energy consumption¹. Even though the overall energy demand in India has increased, its per capita energy consumption is still very low compared to other developing countries.

Statement of the Problem

India is the world's third-largest energy consuming country due to the rising incomes and improving standards of living. Energy use has doubled since 2000, with 80% of demand being met by coal, oil and solid biomass (IEA, 2021). India will soon overtake China to become the country with the largest population. The ever increasing demand for energy can lead to more and more dependency on fossil fuels which in turn can contribute to

environmental degradation, Greenhouse Gas emissions and climate change. Being a developing country, to achieve adequate economic growth, India has to continue its productive activities. In this era of Sustainable development, the study focusses on measures to be adopted by India to achieve sustainability in energy usage without harming the environment and at the same time not curtailing its productive activities.

Objectives

1. To understand energy scenario in India
2. To identify key energy and economic indicators of India.
3. To investigate how solar energy can act as an energy source for sustainable development.

Research Methodology

The study has used various secondary literature and sources of data available both from print and electronic media. The data required for the present study were collected from secondary sources such as World Energy Outlook internet and similar sources.

Need of the Study

The study tries to explore the opportunities and challenges ahead for India as it march towards the objective of providing reliable, affordable and sustainable energy to a growing population. India has seen huge success in its recent energy development, but several challenges still exist. The covid-19 pandemic has added to the challenges and some of the problems include lack of reliable electricity supply for many consumers; continued reliance on solid biomass leading to poor air quality and environmental pollution. This study tries to explore how India could mobilise an additional increase in clean energy investment leading to a decline in emissions, while accelerating its progress towards a range of sustainable development goals.

¹ <https://mea.gov.in/articles-in-indian-media.htm?dtl/13586/Lighting+up+with+renewables>

Energy Scenario in India

Coal, oil, and natural gas are the three primary commercial energy sources in India and coal was the largest source of energy. Even though the dependency on commercial fuels are increasing in India, almost 40 % of the rural households still depend on non-commercial energy sources like fire-wood, crop residue and animal waste. Growth in energy supply has not kept pace with increasing demand and therefore, India continue to face serious energy shortages which in turn has led to increased dependency on imports to meet its energy demand.

Indicators of Energy and Economic Growth

Energy is one of the key input for economic growth and availability of energy and the growth of a nation are directly related. Hence, energy consumption and per capita gross national product are positively correlated. For example, per capita energy consumption in USA was 15.5 times and in Japan 8 times that of India (IEA/OECD). Increased dependency on non-renewable sources of energy can lead to its depletion, contributing to environmental pollution and making it difficult to meet the needs of future generations. Development should be sustainable which means that the needs of the present generation should be met without compromising the ability of future generations to

meet their own needs. Renewable energy sources is a viable option to achieve a sustainable energy use protecting the environment. India has a great potential to generate power from renewable energy sources like small hydro, biomass, wind and solar energy. Greater reliance on renewable energy sources offers enormous economic, social, and environmental benefits and can help in sustainable energy usage. The energy demand in India has been increasing due to several factors like expanding economy, population, urbanisation and industrialization. This has led to increased demand for construction materials like steel and cement which in turn spurs the demand for energy usage especially non-renewable energy in manufacturing sector. The following figure clearly shows the increased demand for energy per capita and other key indicators in India as a percentage of global averages. The per capita demand of coal has increased considerably which shows that the non-renewable energy usage has increased in 2019 compared to 2000. The increased use of non-renewable energy sources can contribute to environmental pollution and emission of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) resulting in global warming.

Figure: 1 Key indicators in India as a percentage of global averages

Source: World Energy Outlook- Special report on India, 2021, IEA

India which is rich in renewable sources of energy like wind and solar energy has tend for an explosive growth slowly overtaking coal generated power generation. At present solar as a source of energy accounts for approximately 4% of India's electricity generation and coal close to 70% (IEA. 2021). By 2040, this scenario can be changed by India concentrating more on renewable sources of power generation. India can reach the target of 450 GW of renewable capacity by 2030. Also India has cost competitiveness in terms of solar energy, which out-

competes *existing* coal-fired power by 2030. Innovative approaches along with investments in renewables like solar power should be promoted to meet India's energy needs, through applications such as rooftop solar, solar thermal heating, and water pumps etc. The projections shows that the investment in renewable sources of energy like solar energy tend to increase by 2030. Solar PV capacity also tend to increase even though the demand for coal is also increasing (See Fig 2).

Figure 2: Annual average clean energy-related investment and activity indicators by sector in the SDS²

Source: World Energy Outlook 2021

In order to achieve sustainable energy usage, India should slowly reduce the dependency on non-renewable energy sources and shift towards more of renewable energy. India can make use of the renewable energy sources which is abundant in our country to its advantage. Cost effective technology and investment should be promoted so that renewable energy can be made available to all sections of population at a competitive price. India should try to reduce its dependency on fossil fuels and concentrate more towards the usage of clean energy.

Figure 3: India's share of selected global indicators in the STEPS³

Source: World Energy Outlook 2021-Special Report on India, IEA

² The **Sustainable Development Scenario** explores how India could mobilise an additional surge in clean energy investment to produce an early peak and rapid subsequent decline in emissions, consistent with a longer-term drive to net zero, while accelerating progress towards a range of other sustainable development goals.

³ The **Stated Policies Scenario** (STEPS) provides a balanced assessment of the direction in which India's energy system is heading, based on today's policy settings and constraints and an assumption that the spread of Covid-19 is largely brought under control in 2021.

Conclusion

Access to affordable and reliable electricity is critical to a country's growth and prosperity. Greater reliance on renewable energy sources offers enormous economic, social, and environmental benefits and can help in sustainable energy usage. India which is rich in renewable sources of energy like wind and solar energy should utilize this advantage to achieve an explosive growth overtaking coal generated power sector. The study stresses that Innovative approaches along with investments in renewables like solar power should be promoted to meet India's energy needs, through applications such as rooftop solar, solar thermal heating, and water pumps etc. As rightly pointed out by the Indian Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi at the climate conference in Paris in 2015, the world must turn to the sun to meet its future energy demands. The Cochin International Airport Limited (CIAL) in Kerala became the first airport in the world which operates entirely on solar power. CIAL has set an example and confirming the belief that India can rely on solar power and achieve clean energy usage towards achieving sustainable development. Sustainable growth concentrating on renewable energy sources can be an alternative as India progress towards its projected growth path without hampering environmental sustainability.

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